

XTreeAD: Explainable Boosting Trees for Anomaly Detection in Cloud-native Services

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Abstract—Cloud-native microservice architectures are increasingly adopted in modern networked systems, including virtualized infrastructures and critical domains such as Healthcare 4.0. Ensuring their reliability requires timely anomaly detection and accurate root-cause analysis (RCA), despite challenges from service-level dependencies and indirect fault propagation. Traditional methods based on statistical thresholds or rule-based heuristics often lack the expressiveness to capture complex metric interactions and treat RCA as a separate, post hoc task. We propose XTreeAD, an explainable, supervised framework for anomaly detection and root-cause localization in microservice-based systems. XTreeAD uses an XGBoost classifier to detect anomalous system states from monitored performance and resource utilization metrics, and applies SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to compute per-service feature attributions. These are aggregated and combined with the service-call graph in a dependency-aware ranking algorithm to identify likely faulty services. Experiments on a public available dataset show that XTreeAD outperforms established baselines in detection precision, localization accuracy, and runtime efficiency.

Index Terms—anomaly detection, cloud-native, explainable artificial intelligence, root-cause analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Microservice architectures are widely adopted for building cloud-native applications due to their scalability, modularity, and operational agility. They play a central role in emerging networked systems, particularly in the transition from Beyond 5G to 6G infrastructures, where microservice-based applications and Virtualized or Cloud-Native Network Functions (VNFs/CNFs) enable dynamic and resilient network services. Efficient orchestration and scheduling of VNFs have become central to delivering adaptive and reliable services in virtualized network environments [1]. At the same time, the growing interconnection of such distributed systems introduces new security challenges, including resilience against large-scale and stochastic attacks [2]. Beyond telecommunications, such architectures are now essential for distributed and mission-critical platforms in domains like Healthcare 4.0 [3], where dependable, secure, and continuous service delivery is vital.

However, maintaining operational resilience in such environments remains a significant challenge. The highly distributed and asynchronous nature of microservices, combined with their dynamic inter-dependencies, complicates the task of detecting anomalous behavior. Unlike monolithic systems, where faults often manifest locally, microservice anomalies

can propagate across co-dependent services, resulting in delayed or ambiguous failure symptoms. As systems grow in complexity and inter-service dependencies, timely anomaly detection and accurate root-cause localization become increasingly difficult.

Traditional approaches for anomaly detection and root-cause analysis (RCA) in microservice systems rely heavily on statistical thresholds, clustering, or rule-based heuristics [4]–[6]. These methods are lightweight but often assume metric independence and struggle with noisy, high-dimensional monitoring data. RCA techniques are typically applied post hoc and depend on simplistic anomaly triggers, limiting diagnostic precision.

BARO [7] addresses this by integrating anomaly detection and RCA into a unified unsupervised pipeline. It uses multivariate change-point detection followed by a statistical hypothesis testing technique to rank anomalous services. While BARO avoids manual thresholds and prior system knowledge, its statistical models are less expressive than learned ones and can incur high computational cost.

AI-based methods for anomaly detection, both supervised and unsupervised, have demonstrated strong performance in detecting complex anomalies [8], [9]. However, there are limited prior works in the context of metric-based, microservice anomaly detection. ADS [10] applies supervised learning to detect anomalies in containerized microservices using performance metrics and fault injection. While effective at identifying anomalous behavior, it does not support root-cause localization and provides limited interpretability.

To address the opacity of black-box models, the field of explainable AI (XAI) has emerged as a means to improve transparency, accountability, and trust in AI-based systems [11]. A very popular, model-agnostic technique, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [12], provides feature-level attributions by quantifying each input’s contribution to a model’s prediction. In the context of anomaly detection, SHAP can highlight which system metrics most strongly influenced the anomalous classification. Although such methods do not capture causal relationships explicitly, their attributions often reflect meaningful patterns of abnormal behavior observed in the system. When augmented with simple structural system knowledge, they can enable lightweight and scalable root-cause localization without requiring full causal graph inference, which is often noise-

Fig. 1. System Model for end-to-end Anomaly Detection and Root-Cause Service Localization

sensitive, and computationally intensive in practice.

In this work, we propose XTreeAD, a framework that integrates supervised anomaly detection with explainable root-cause localization. Our method employs an Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [13] classifier to label system states as normal or anomalous, and uses SHAP values to identify influential services contributing to the anomaly. To incorporate structural context, XTreeAD leverages the service dependency graph in a lightweight ranking procedure that prioritizes likely root causes while accounting for symptom propagation across services. The main contributions of this work are the following:

- 1) We propose a supervised anomaly detection framework tailored to microservice architectures, employing tree-based learning with explainable outputs.
- 2) We develop a dependency-aware, root-cause localization strategy that integrates SHAP feature attributions with the service dependency graph.
- 3) We conduct experiments on a public available dataset, demonstrating superior detection accuracy, localization precision, and runtime performance compared to established baselines.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows. Section II introduces the system model and problem formulation. Section III presents the XTreeAD framework. Section IV describes the experimental setup, baselines, and results. Section V concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Figure 1 illustrates the system model considered in this work, representing a cloud-native application composed of monitored microservices. This section describes the structure of monitoring data and service interactions and defines the supervised anomaly detection setting along with the two main problem objectives: identifying anomalous behavior and localizing the responsible service.

A. Cloud-Native Microservice Monitoring

A cloud-native application is as a set of N interdependent microservices, indexed as $\mathcal{M} = \{m_i\}_{i=1}^N$. Cloud-native systems are commonly monitored and orchestrated using container-based platforms (e.g., Kubernetes) that enable observability, scalability, and service-level isolation.

a) *Per-service monitoring*.: Each microservice m_i is continuously monitored through a collection of metrics that characterize its behavior and operational state. These metrics may include resource-level indicators such as CPU usage and memory consumption, as well as application-level metrics like request latency, error rates, and throughput, which capture how the service behaves from an external perspective. For a number of d_v monitored metrics, the collected values are concatenated into a per-service feature vector:

$$\mathbf{v}_{t,i} = [u_{t,i}^{(1)}, u_{t,i}^{(2)}, \dots, u_{t,i}^{(d_v)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{d_v}. \quad (1)$$

Stacking the N vectors produces a system-wide state vector of length d :

$$\mathbf{x}_t = [\mathbf{v}_{t,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{t,N}] \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad d = N d_v. \quad (2)$$

b) *Service dependency graph*: Microservices interact through synchronous remote procedure calls (RPCs), forming a dynamic web of dependencies across the system. We represent the application structure as a directed service dependency graph:

$$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{E}), \quad (3)$$

where an edge $(m_i \rightarrow m_j) \in \mathcal{E}$ indicates that service m_i invokes service m_j . This graph captures the flow of control and data between services, and plays a critical role in understanding how anomalies can propagate downstream or manifest indirectly. For each service, we define its downstream set:

$$\mathcal{C}(m_i) = \{m_j \in \mathcal{M} \mid (m_i \rightarrow m_j) \in \mathcal{E}\}, \quad (4)$$

which contains the direct dependencies of m_i . For example, if m_1 invokes m_2 and m_3 , then $\mathcal{C}(m_1) = \{m_2, m_3\}$.

B. Supervised Anomaly Detection

A system state \mathbf{x}_t is labeled anomalous ($y_t = 1$) if a service failure (e.g., CPU hog, memory leak, packet loss) is present. Otherwise, the state is considered normal ($y_t = 0$). Labels are derived from historical incident logs and synthetic fault-injection experiments. Collecting T labeled system states yields the dataset:

$$\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_t, y_t)\}_{t=1}^T, \quad y_t \in \{0, 1\}. \quad (5)$$

C. Problem Definition

Given a time window of length W , the monitored system defines, for each $t \geq W$, an observation window:

$$\mathbf{X}_{t-W+1:t} = [\mathbf{x}_{t-W+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_t] \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times d}, \quad (6)$$

The problem consists of two sub-tasks:

- 1) **Anomaly detection.** A *detector* $f: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ assigns a predicted label $\hat{y}_t = f(\mathbf{x}_t)$ to each system state. Let $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t-W+1:t} = [\hat{y}_{t-W+1}, \dots, \hat{y}_t]$ denote the predicted label sequence for the window. The window $\mathbf{X}_{t-W+1:t}$ is declared anomalous if any of its states is classified as anomalous:

$$z_t = \max(\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t-W+1:t}) = 1. \quad (7)$$

- 2) **Root-cause localization.** Given an anomalous window ($\mathbf{X}_{t^*-W+1:t^*}, z_{t^*} = 1$), the *explainer* aggregates feature-attribution scores across all predicted anomalous states to compute a per-service attribution score $s(m_i)$. It then incorporates the downstream sets $\mathcal{C}(m_i)$, derived from the service dependency graph \mathcal{G} , to adjust scores based on dependency structure. The final output is a ranked list $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{M}$ of the top- k services most likely responsible for the anomaly.

III. XTREEAD FRAMEWORK

This section presents the XTreeAD framework for explainable anomaly detection in microservice-based systems. The framework comprises of three core components: (i) an XGBoost-based anomaly detector, (ii) SHAP-based feature attribution, and (iii) a dependency-aware root-cause localization module.

A. XGBoost Anomaly Detection

Given the labeled dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_t, y_t)\}_{t=1}^T$, the anomaly detector in XTreeAD is trained using XGBoost [13], a scalable implementation of extreme gradient boosting. The model takes the form

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \eta h_m(\mathbf{x}), \quad (8)$$

where each h_m is a regression tree, M denotes the number of boosting rounds, and η is the learning rate. The ensemble minimizes the regularized logistic loss

$$\mathcal{L}(f) = \sum_{t=1}^T \ell(y_t, p_t) + \Omega(f), \quad (9)$$

where p_t is the predicted probability

$$p_t = \sigma(f(\mathbf{x}_t)), \quad (10)$$

with $\sigma(\cdot)$ denoting the sigmoid function. A system state is flagged as anomalous when $p_t > \tau$, and an observation window is considered anomalous if it contains at least one such state.

B. SHAP Feature Attributions

To enable explainability, TreeSHAP [14] is applied to interpret the detector's output in terms of per-feature contributions. For each anomalous system state \mathbf{x}_t , TreeSHAP produces a vector $\phi_t = (\phi_{t,1}, \dots, \phi_{t,d})$ of contribution scores. Only the positive components defined as $\phi_{t,i}^+ = \max(\phi_{t,i}, 0)$, are retained, as these correspond to features that increase the detector's confidence in an anomaly. In the context of root-cause localization, such features are more indicative of abnormal behavior. These scores are then aggregated across the set \mathcal{A} of anomalous states within the current window:

$$\psi_i = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{A}|} \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{A}} \phi_{t',i}^+. \quad (11)$$

Based on the ordering of service features in the system state vector, the aggregated feature scores vector is reshaped as

$$\boldsymbol{\psi} = [\psi_{1,1}, \dots, \psi_{1,d_v}, \psi_{2,1}, \dots, \psi_{N,d_v}] \quad (12)$$

to produce an $N \times d_v$ matrix $\boldsymbol{\Psi}$. The indexing is defined such that $\psi_{i,j} \triangleq \psi_{(i-1)d_v+j}$, where $\psi_{i,j}$ denotes the aggregated SHAP score for metric j of service m_i . The importance of service m_i is computed by summing its row:

$$s(m_i) = \sum_{j=1}^{d_v} \Psi_{i,j} = \sum_{j=1}^{d_v} \psi_{(i-1)d_v+j}, \quad m_i \in \mathcal{M}. \quad (13)$$

Algorithm 1: Root-Cause Service Localization

Input: $\{s(m_i)\}$: per-service scores, k : number of root-cause candidates, $\{\mathcal{C}(m_i)\}_{i=1}^N$: downstream sets, τ : tolerance

Output: \mathcal{S} : ranked list of k services

$\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \text{TOP}_k$ services by $s(m_i)$;

Normalize $s(m_i)$ over \mathcal{S} ;

repeat

foreach (i, j) with $i < j$ in \mathcal{S} **do**

if $m_j \in \mathcal{C}(m_i)$ **and** $s(m_j) \geq \tau s(m_i)$ **then**

 swap m_i and m_j ;

end

end

until no swaps;

return \mathcal{S}

C. Root-Cause Service Localization

When service m_j is downstream of m_i , their metrics, and subsequently their SHAP scores, are correlated due to fault propagation. In such cases, a naive ranking based solely on $s(m_i)$ may overemphasize upstream services that are affected by, but not responsible for, the anomaly. To address this, the ranking is adjusted to favor downstream services.

Instead of operating directly on the service dependency graph \mathcal{G} , local downstream sets $\mathcal{C}(m_i)$ are used for each service. Starting from the top- k services by $s(m_i)$, upstream-downstream pairs (m_i, m_j) are iteratively swapped when $m_j \in \mathcal{C}(m_i)$ and $s(m_j) \geq \tau s(m_i)$. The tolerance $\tau \in (0, 1)$ determines how significant the score difference must be to justify a swap. It acts as a measure against always demoting upstream services below their downstream counterparts, hence overlooking cases where the failure actually initiates there. Only when a downstream service has a score sufficiently close to its upstream caller is it interpreted as a likely root cause and promoted in the ranking.

The procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1. The final output $\mathcal{S} = [m_{(1)}, \dots, m_{(k)}]$ is a ranking that prioritizes services most likely to be responsible for the anomaly, while accounting for likely propagation effects.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The proposed framework is evaluated on its ability to detect anomalies and localize their root causes in a cloud-native microservice setting.

A. Dataset

Evaluation is based on the *Online Boutique* (Figure 2) part of the BARO dataset [7], which captures resource-, performance-, and network-level metrics from ten microservices operating under a steady workload. Four types of faults are considered: CPU overload, memory leak, network delay, and packet loss. These are injected into five target services (adservice, cartservice, checkoutservice, currencyservice, productcatalogue), with each (fault, service) combination repeated five times, resulting in 100 labeled failure cases.

To ensure chronological separation between training and test data, the first three fault-injection runs in each scenario are used for training, while the fourth and fifth runs are reserved for testing. This split preserves temporal order, prevents data leakage, and yields an approximate 60/40 ratio between training and test snapshots across both normal and anomalous cases.

B. Experimental Setup

A preliminary inspection of the BARO traces has shown that observable metric deviations typically emerge a few seconds after the fault-injection timestamp t_{inj} . Including training instances too close to t_{inj} risks diluting the anomalous class with healthy data, thereby confusing the model. To address this, the first 10 seconds following each injection are excluded from

Fig. 2. Online Boutique Dependency Graph

training. This pre-processing is not applied on testing samples to enable fair comparison with the baselines.

The XGBoost detector is trained using 300 trees, a learning rate of 0.1, depth-3 weak learners, a minimum child weight of 5, and row/column subsampling rates of 0.8 and 0.6, respectively. These settings are selected to balance model capacity with regularization. The downstream-upstream score tolerance in the localization algorithm (Algorithm 1) is fixed at $\tau = 0.6$.

C. Evaluation Metrics

To assess the performance of the proposed framework, separate metrics are used for anomaly detection and root-cause localization.

1) *Anomaly Detection*: Detection performance is evaluated at the observation window level to enable direct comparison with baseline methods that also operate on windowed input. For each window \mathbf{X}_t , the detector produces a binary label, which is compared against ground-truth labels derived from the fault injection schedule. Standard classification metrics are used in this context: *Precision*, *Recall*, and *F1-score*.

2) *Root-Cause Analysis*: The quality of root-cause localization is assessed using the ranking-based metrics $AC@k$ (Accuracy at k) and its cumulative variant $Avg@k$, commonly used in this scenario, as defined in [7]. $AC@k$ reflects the proportion of cases where at least one true root cause appears among the top- k ranked services. $Avg@k$ averages this success rate across all cut-offs $j = 1, \dots, k$, providing a cumulative measure of ranking performance.

D. Baselines

We compare against two established approaches for anomaly detection and root-cause localization in microservice-based systems:

- 1) **BARO** [7]. A recent end-to-end framework that combines Multivariate Bayesian Online Change-Point Detection (M-BOCPD) for anomaly detection with a statistical hypothesis test for localization. Services are ranked by the magnitude of post-change metric deviations.
- 2) **N-Sigma** [5] [6]. A simple statistical baseline that flags anomalies when any metric exceeds $N = 3$ standard deviations. Root causes are inferred by ranking services based on cumulative deviation magnitudes.

E. Experimental Results

Tables I–III compare **XTreeAD** against the BARO and N-Sigma baselines in terms of anomaly detection performance, root-cause localization accuracy, and computational efficiency.

1) *Comparison to Baselines*: This subsection reports the core quantitative results of the evaluation. Performance is measured in terms of detection quality, localization accuracy, and runtime cost.

a) *Anomaly detection*: (Table I). All methods achieve perfect window-level recall, indicating that all injected faults have been successfully detected. However, significant differences are observed in precision. XTreeAD has achieved a precision of 0.91, substantially outperforming BARO (0.80) and N-Sigma (0.60), resulting also in the highest F1-score of 0.95. The precision gain can be attributed to the tree-based learning capability of XTreeAD, which captures multivariate metric dependencies and complex decision boundaries more selectively. Unlike the univariate N-Sigma thresholding and the correlation-driven M-BOCPD used in BARO, XTreeAD is more capable to distinguish between failure-induced and unrelated metric fluctuations, thereby reducing false positives.

TABLE I
ANOMALY DETECTION RESULTS COMPARING XTREEAD, BARO, AND N-SIGMA.

Method	Precision	Recall	F1
N-Sigma	0.60	1.00	0.75
BARO	0.80	1.00	0.89
XTreeAD	0.91	1.00	0.95

b) *Root-cause localization*: (Table II). XTreeAD also demonstrates consistently strong performance in root-cause identification across all ranking depths. At the strictest cutoff, $AC@1 = 0.78$ shows that the true root cause is ranked first in nearly 80% of cases. This exceeds BARO (0.72) and N-Sigma (0.45). Across larger candidate pools, XTreeAD maintains the lead or remains competitive, achieving an $Avg@5$ of 0.90. These results confirm that the SHAP-based feature attribution, when combined with dependency-aware ranking, offers reliable localization of the root-cause services.

TABLE II
ROOT-CAUSE LOCALIZATION ACCURACY AT VARIOUS TOP- k CUTOFFS.

Method	$Avg@5$	$AC@1$	$AC@2$	$AC@3$	$AC@4$	$AC@5$
N-Sigma	0.72	0.45	0.65	0.78	0.82	0.90
BARO	0.88	0.72	0.88	0.90	0.90	0.97
XTreeAD	0.90	0.78	0.90	0.93	0.95	0.95

c) *Runtime efficiency*: (Table III). XTreeAD processes anomaly detection at approximately 0.01 seconds per window, offering three orders of magnitude speedup compared to BARO’s M-BOCPD pipeline (44.8 seconds), and achieving comparable performance to N-Sigma (0.12 seconds). Root-cause localization completes in around 0.03 seconds, which is slightly slower than the lightweight statistical methods (both under 0.01 seconds), but still suitable for real-time use-cases. These results demonstrate that XTreeAD provides a favorable balance between accuracy and computational cost.

TABLE III
RUNTIME PERFORMANCE OF ANOMALY DETECTION AND ROOT-CAUSE LOCALIZATION.

Method	Detection Time (s)	RCA Time (s)	Total Time (s)
N-Sigma	0.12	0.01	0.13
BARO	44.83	0.01	44.84
XTreeAD	0.01	0.03	0.04

2) *Analysis of SHAP Feature Attributions*: To further interpret the behavior of XTreeAD, we examine the SHAP values generated by the explainer. Both global patterns and local case studies are presented.

a) *Global attribution patterns*: Figure 3 presents the mean SHAP values aggregated over anomalous and normal windows. In both cases, it is evident that `checkoutservice_latency` has a dominant role on influencing the model’s predictions. This is easily justified by the application architecture (Figure 2), since `checkoutservice` is an upstream service of all the services that are injected with failures. During failures, the attribution mass spreads across several metrics, mostly related to latency. In contrast, healthy periods exhibit concentration on `checkoutservice_latency`. This shift suggests that XTreeAD identifies anomalies through a distributed symptom pattern rather than isolated outliers.

Fig. 3. Mean SHAP values for (a) anomalous and (b) normal windows.

b) *Local attribution case studies*: Figure 4 presents SHAP waterfall plots for two representative failure cases. In Figure 4(a), a network delay is injected into `currencysservice`. The dominant SHAP contributions originate from `currencysservice_latency` (+3.45)

and `checkoutservice_latency` (+3.35), reflecting delay propagation from the affected service to its upstream. In Figure 4(b), a CPU overload on `paymentservice` results in high attribution scores on both latency (+5.23) and CPU usage (+2.90) for that service. In both cases, secondary effects—such as memory usage increases on `recommendationservice`—are also surfaced, while unaffected metrics receive near-zero or negative attributions. This results in an interpretable attribution profile that aligns with the final ranked list.

Fig. 4. SHAP waterfall plots for (a) a network delay in `currencyservice` and (b) a CPU overload in `paymentservice`.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented XTreeAD, a framework for explainable anomaly detection and root-cause localization in cloud-native microservice environments. The approach combines an XGBoost-based detector with SHAP feature attributions to provide actionable insights into anomalous behavior. A lightweight ranking adjustment, informed by service dependencies, enables effective distinction between propagated symptoms and true root causes. Evaluation on the BARO dataset has demonstrated that XTreeAD achieves high precision and recall in anomaly detection, accurate root-cause

localization, and low inference latency. SHAP-based attribution further enhances interpretability at both global and local levels, supporting real-time diagnostics. An interesting future direction is to extend the current framework to more fine-grained root-cause localization at the metrics level, by identifying not only the faulty services but also the specific contributing metrics.

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